

GAPIRISH QOBILIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QO‘LLANILADIGAN ZAMONAVIY METODLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda gapirish qobiliyatidagi turli xil muammolar o‘rganilib, nutq rivojlanishida qo‘llaniladigan zamonaviy metodlar ko‘rib chiqiladi va bu bo‘yicha muhim natijalar keltiriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: zamonaviy metodlar, nutq, CLT, TBL, gapirish qobiliyati, tadqiqotlar.

Abstract. This study examines various problems related to speaking ability, explores modern methods used in speech development, and presents important results in this area.

Keywords: modern methods, speech, CLT, TBL, speaking ability, research.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматриваются различные проблемы, связанные с навыками говорения, анализируются современные методы, применяемые в развитии речи, а также приводятся важные результаты по данной теме.

Ключевые слова: современные методы, речь, коммуникативная теория речи, теория командной работы, устная речь, исследование.

Kirish. Hozirgi kunda gapirish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga bo‘lgan talab ortishi bilan birga, bu masala dolzarb ilmiy muammolardan biri hisoblanadi. So‘nggi yillarda turli xil yoshdagi bolalarning nutq qobiliyati bilan bog‘liq muammolarga olimlar tomonidan zamonaviy metodlar ishlab chiqilmoqda. Bu tadqiqot olib borilishidan maqsad CLT (communicative language teaching), TBLT (task-based language teaching), Role play kabi metodlarni, ularni hayotda to‘g‘ri qo‘llashni o‘rganish. Shu bilan birga bu metodlarning nutq rivojlanishida tutgan asosiy o‘rni va ahamiyatining qanchalik muhimligi o‘rganiladi.

Asosiy qism. “The development of speaking skills involves not only the acquisition of grammatical and lexical accuracy, but also fluency, coherence, and appropriateness of language use in various social contexts. Educational institution have increasingly recognized the importance of creating an environment that supports communicative competence. This is achieved by integrating a variety of contemporary methodologies that foster authentic communication and meaningful interaction among students. One of the foundational modern approaches is the communicative language teaching (CLT) method, which emphasizes real-life communication as the core of language learning. This approach encourages students to express their thoughts, negotiate meaning, and participate in collaborative tasks that mirror genuine conversational settings. The CLT method allows for the flexible use of language and accommodates individual differences by prioritizing the conveyance of meaning over

the rigid application of grammatical rules". (Alamuratov E.U. International journal of artificial intelligence, p. 614)

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti filologiya fakulteti o'qituvchisi Alamuratov Elyor Umarali o'g'li tomonidan yozilgan ushbu maqolada gapirish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda turli xil metodlardan foydalanish ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Mazkur masalada gapirishda grammatikaning ahamiyati pastroqligi, nutq ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun eshitish (listening), o'qish (reading) kabi turli xil usullardan foydalanish ham tavsiya etiladi. CLT metodida esa real hayotda, masalan o'quvchilar orasida aloqa vositasini yaxshilash uchun ishlatiladigan turli xil guruh muhokamalari va shunga o'xshash mashqlardan foydalaniladi.

Mazkur masala yuzasidan Soon Ming Hui va Melor Md Yunus olib borgan tadqiqotlar ham muhim ahamiyatga ega: "Speaking is a fundamental life skill one should possess through verbal language to convey an idea to another individual. It involves physical and mental processes to ensure an adequate flow of ideas between the two parties. In today's globalized marketplace, it is imperative to display a good command of spoken English, as solid attachment can be forged between the two speakers, regardless of their backgrounds and practices (Pedagogy et al., 2020). One of the ultimate goals of teaching English in an ESL context is facilitating communicative competence among the pupils. However, it is not uncommon for many ESL pupils to feel challenged to speak fluently and accurately in English (Rao, 2019). In relation to this, ESL teachers ought to provide extra attention and numerous practice grounds for their pupils to apply the language in various communicative circumstances". (Soon Ming Hui; Melor Md Yunus. Journal of language teaching and research, p. 1516). Ularning fikricha, gapirish bu og'zaki nutqda kerak bo'ladigan asosiy vosita hisoblanadi. Bu olimlar gapirish ko'nikmalarini ingliz tili bilan bog'lab tadqiqot o'tkazishgan. Ingliz tilini o'quvchilar orasida metodlar orqali o'rgatish va ularning gapirish(speaking) mahoratlarini oshiradigan mashq va metodlar yuzasidan izlanishlar olib borishgan.

"In recent years the process of teaching grammar was associated with the traditional methods, including learning the numerous rules and endless repetitions of the structures, which in the long run in the course of time revealed to be ineffective in teaching students to communicate. Fluent conversational English as an objective of every student can be gained in the process of language learning by using the communicative approach, introduced by a British linguist D.A. Wilkins and specified in his book titled "Notional Syllabuses" as communicative language teaching (Richards & Rodgers, 2001, p. 154), with the focus on the speech activity in the process of learning. To communicative approach appeared latest embraced many useful elements from other approaches: performing tasks from the Task-Based Language Learning (Bhandari 2020), reproducing words and phrases from the audiolingual approach, making up situations close to reality from the natural approach and working in teams from the cooperative language learning approach" (Richards & Rodgers, 2001, p. 165) (V.Berezenko, O.Cherkhava, Y.Musiienko. Advanced education, p. 89).

Olingan natijalarni boshqa tadqiqotlar bilan solishtirganda, barcha olimlar gapirish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda hayotiy tajribalaridan kelib chiqqan holda zamonaviy metodlar orqali til o'rgatish va nutq rivojlanishida bu metodlarning qay darajada kerakligi, ahamiyati va asosiy omillarini o'rgatishgan. E.U. Alamuratov gapirishni rivojlantirishda qo'llash mumkin bo'lgan CLT (communicative language teaching)

haqida tadqiqot olib brogan bo'lsa, Victoriia B., Olesya Ch., Yuliia M. kabilar TBL (task-based language learning) haqida izlanishgan. Natijalarning amaliy ahamiyati shundan iboratki, ikkala metod ham gapirish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda sezilarli darajada yordam beradi. CLT (communicative language learning)da ko'proq bir-biri bilan o'zaro muloqot qilib nutq rivojlantirilsa, TBL (task-based language learning) metodida turli xil mashg'ulotlar orqali gapirish ko'nikmalari rivojlanadi. Demak, har ikkala metodda ham birdek foyda olishimiz mumkin. O'quvchilarni ko'proq bir-biri bilan muloqot qilishga undaydigan mashqlar va topshiriqlar bajartirish ham maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

Xulosa. Tadqiqot natijasida quyidagi xulosalarga kelindi: gapirishni rivojlantirishda yanada ko'proq ahamiyat berish; bu soha uchun kerakli bo'lgan metodlarni qayta ko'rib chiqish va mustahkamlash; nutq qobiliyatini rivojlantiradigan zamonaviy metodlarni ko'paytirish va ulardan to'g'ri foydalanish zarur.

Mazkur ish til o'rganishda gapirishni rivojlantiradigan metodlarni ommalashtirish va ulardan keng ko'lamda foydalanishga xizmat qiladi. Kelgusida zamonaviy metodlarni ko'paytirish va uni ommaga tatbiq etishda tadqiqotlar olib boorish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Ushbu tadqiqot gapirish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda qo'llaniladigan zamonaviy metodlarni yanada chuqur o'rganish zarurligini ko'rsatdi.

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